

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B402
 Date: 19/09/08
 Take Off: 08:46:33Z
 Landing: 14:06:59Z
 Flight Time 5h 20m 26s

Campaign: VACAR + ADIENT

Operating Area: E Coast – Aberdeen to E Anglia

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Simon Osborne	Met Office	Y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	Y
6	Core Chem / AVAPS / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	N/Y
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	Y
8	ARIES / Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	N/N/Y
9	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	N
10	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	Y
11	AMS / SP2	Gavin McMeeking	University of Manchester	N
12	TAFTS	Paul Green	Imperial College	N
13	MARSS/DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office	N
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

Flight Track:

B402 Track 19-SEP-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B402
 Date: 19 Sept 2008
 Project: VACAR and ADIENT
 Location: E Coast - Aberdeen to E Anglia

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
083140		Start-Up	-.04 kft	127	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
084102		ASP	-.04 kft	055	Open
084633		T/O	0.82 kft	297	Cranfield
092120		Video	27.0 kft	341	Start recording all 4
094043	095504	Run 1.1	27.0 kft	345	Launch Sonde #01 @A
094411		Sonde	27.0 kft	345	Launch #02
094738		Sonde	27.0 kft	344	Launch #03
095124		Sonde	27.0 kft	344	Launch #04
095343		Sonde	27.0 kft	346	Launch #05
095332		Event	27.0 kft	345	Ovhd B
100019	101301	Run 1.2	27.0 kft	098	B-A
100201		Sonde	27.0 kft	195	Launch #06
100430		Sonde	27.0 kft	175	Launch #07
100601		Event	27.0 kft	174	Sat Overpass
100722		Sonde	27.0 kft	173	Launch #08
101054		Sonde	27.0 kft	174	Launch #09,@A
102104	103113	Profile 1	27.0 - 17.1 kft	001	A-B, 1kfp
103438	104251	Profile 1	17.0 - 9.0 kft	167	Interrupt at A
104741	105700	Profile 1	9.0 - 2.9 kft	345	A-B Int at 3k,ATC
105028		Event	6.2 kft	348	500fpm
105847	110446	Profile 2.1	2.9 - -.18 kft	348	3k-100',End at B
110749	111147	Profile 2.1	3.8 - 5.8 kft	177	4k-6k' ,Q1023
111148	111640	Profile 2.2	5.8 - 3.8 kft	169	Q1021-ATC
111640	111925	Profile 2.3	3.8 - 5.2 kft	173	4k'- 5.5k'
111925	112242	Profile 2.4	5.2 - 3.8 kft	172	5.5k'-4k'
112242	112411	Profile 2.5	3.8 - 4.5 kft	173	4k'-4.75k@A
112550	113422	Run 2	4.6 - 4.5 kft	018	4.75k' A-B In cloud
113422	114306	Profile 3	4.5 - 0.28 kft	345	4.75-0.5k'
113532		JW & Nevz	3.8 kft	345	Zero
114414	125342	Run 3.1	0.32 - 0.11 kft	209	B-A 0.5k'
114650		Heimann	0.20 kft	172	Cal
114854		Event	0.20 kft	175	Q1025
115732		Event	0.18 kft	173	Q1026
120225		Event	0.18 kft	180	A
121016		Event	0.16 kft	181	Q1027
121640		Event	0.20 kft	145	WP 78
121837		Event	0.12 kft	151	Q1028
122438		Event	0.14 kft	144	WP 79
124136		Event	0.25 kft	143	WP 80
124350		Event	0.12 kft	155	Q1029
125342	130014	Profile 4.1	0.11 - 6.5 kft	150	0.5k-6.5k', 1kfp
130014	130858	Profile 4.2	6.5 - 0.13 kft	153	6.5k-500'
130232		Event	4.8 kft	136	WP 87
130440		Event	2.5 kft	106	1nm Abeam Weybourne
130912	133654	Run 3.2	0.10 - 0.27 kft	105	1kfp
131045		Heimann	0.18 kft	112	Cal
131141		Event	0.18 kft	139	WP 40
132339		Event	0.38 kft	265	16nm short of WP41
133604		Event	0.16 kft	317	WP 40
133655	134545	Profile 5	0.27 - 10.0 kft	286	1kfp
134323		Event	7.6 kft	291	Abeam Weybourne
134521		Event	9.7 kft	235	WP 87
134730		Video	10.0 kft	233	Stop Recording
140659		Land	-.06 kft	356	Cranfield
141042		Shutdown	-.06 kft	305	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B402 Track 19-SEP-08

Pilot: Alan Roberts

NavData Cycle 2008-9 Expires: Thursday, 25 September 2008.

Scale: 1:3007761 (1 inch = 41.25 naut mi). Printed on 18 Sep 2008

54774946

FliteStar 9.4.2.0

Sortie Flight A402
19th September 2008.
VACAR and Adient

Take off Cranfield 1000L (0900Z)
Land at Cranfield ~1500L (1400Z)

Aims

To underfly the IASI instrument on the Metop satellite (**1006Z overpass**) in a region of boundary layer cloud to test new techniques for assimilating IR satellite data in cloud affected regions. Also to study the radiative and chemical properties of aerosol plumes off the East coast.

Weather

Boundary layer cloud with clear sky conditions above.

Way points

ALPHA = 56N 2 W

BRAVO = 57N 2W

Note that these points should be in area of boundary layer cloud; if necessary these points can be repositioned.

Ampep points: 77, 78, 79, 80, 87, 40, 41

Sortie

1. Take off and transit to point ALPHA 56N 2W to arrive a max attainable altitude (60mins) T+60
2. Fly straight and level run from ALPHA to BRAVO (57N 2W) dropping sondes at T+0, T+3, T+6 and T+9 (10mins) T+70 IASI overpass should occur during middle of either this run or the next
3. Fly straight and level run from BRAVO to ALPHA dropping sondes at 3 min intervals once first sonde has splashed down. (10mins + 2 turn) T+82
4. Profile descent along line ALPHA-BRAVO at 1000ft/min to 100ft reducing to 500ft/min in the boundary layer profiling through the cloud aiming to end at point BRAVO (38mins) T+120
5. Fly series of saw tooth profiles from 1000ft below **cloud tops** to 1000ft above **cloud tops** at 500ft/min between BRAVO and ALPHA (20mins) T+140
6. Fly straight and level run from ALPHA to BRAVO at level in middle of boundary layer cloud (20 mins) T+160 (CVI in **counterflow** mode)
7. Profile descent North turning in profile to arrive at point BRAVO at 500ft heading South. (10mins) T+170
8. Straight and level run from BRAVO to ALPHA at 500ft (this run should be in the aerosol layer and below all cloud – adjust altitudes accordingly). (20mins) T+190
9. Fly to the following AMPEP points at 500ft 77, 78, 79, 80, 87, 40, 41 at 500ft remaining clear of cloud (90mins T+280)
10. Recover to Cranfield (20mins T+300)

Key Instrument Details:

SWS - to look down during high level runs to characterise clouds. Look up during 500ft runs.

ARIES - to look down for most of high level run – (100% during IASI overpass run) but with short (2min) zenith view during other run at high level.

CVI - During high level and profile descent operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

Miss Scientist Notes:

Aim of VACAR is to underfly IASI over boundary layer cloud and characterise the cloud tops. The IR instruments do not see all the way through the clouds so concentrate the saw tooth profiles to characterise the cloud top boundary.

Adient needs to be cloud free at low level adjust altitude as necessary.

Please contact Exeter for guidance on position of plumes before and during flight.

We are expecting that from AMPEP point 40 to 41 you may sample continental plume. If this does not materialise (Exeter will advise) then it may be worth repeatedly crossing expected strong plume gradient between points 40 and 87.

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

VACAR/ADIENT flight B402

19th September 2008

Weather conditions:

High pressure with ridging behind front. Generally a slack southwesterly flow over the operating regions off Scotland and all the way down the east coast.

See MGS visible sat pic below from the day: highlighted is the Sc worked for the VACAR section of the flight. Note the largely clear skies down the east coast too (much of the Sc in the North Sea broke up during the morning). The frontal zone from the previous day had passed down the country leaving broken Sc and Cu behind it (most of the cloud in the sat pic is low cloud).

Summary of the flight:

A very successful sortie was carried out that contained two separate aims: a VACAR part working an area of stratocumulus and an ADIENT part to sample a strong plume advecting off England over the North Sea. The AMS was also tested within cloud using the CVI inlet in counterflow mode. Radiation work (SWS) should be possible during the long ADIENT run.

For the VACAR part of the flight, an area of Sc was chosen before flight that contained no medium or high level cloud. Although this area of cloud evolved during the sortie and dissipated to some extent, we were lucky enough to make our high and low level sections, and sample the cloud microphysics in-situ all with reasonable cloud. Two runs were made between points A (56°N, 1°30'W) and B (57°N, 1°50'W) at FL270 over the Sc sheet. 5 sondes were dropped during Run 1 (sonde 4 GPS failed). 4 sondes were dropped during Run 2 and the IASI overpass also occurred during Run 2 (1006z). It was noted during Run 2 that some breaks were starting to appear in the Sc deck. A broken profile descent was made down to 100ft, staying between A and B and finishing at point B. Cloud was penetrated during the descent and it was seen that the cloud tops were uneven and quite "wispy" i.e. there was not the "crisp" tops often associated with Sc. Vis was very high in the MBL and aerosol loadings were low, very low; the neph hovered around zero (!) for most of the low level bits under the Sc. *I don't think I've seen a MBL containing so little aerosol before.* A series of sawtooths was made from just below cloud base (4000ft) to just above cloud top (5500-6000ft) between pts B and A; five individual profiles were carried out. A SLR (A to B) was then carried out in cloud (skimming cloud tops) at 4750ft so that the AMS could sample cloud drop residuals using the CVI inlet. Both the AMS and CVI showed a successful test of the equipment. A profile descent was made to 500ft to finish around pt B and a SLR was carried out from B to A at 500ft below cloud. Aerosol concs did rise above zero along this run heading south !

At pt A this run was terminated and the AMPEP route was started heading down the east coast at 500ft. Localised plumes were observed downwind of Teeside. Generally high loadings were seen south of pt 79 and super-high loadings south of pt 80. The neph scatt coeff (0.55um) reached $1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-1}$. Good separation was seen in the

three neph wavelengths. PSAP showed a similar pattern as a timeseries to the neph trace. *Uncorrected* SSA was about 0.85 in the heaviest pollution. NO_x values were significant but lower than the mega-high mixing ratios found during B401 in the English Channel (less shipping in the North Sea?). Wet neph growth factors (in terms of scattering) were the standard British ~1.7-1.8 at ~85 % RH. Although the pollution was still heavy, a sawtooth ascent/descent was made from 500ft (started around pt 81) to 7000ft passing pt 87 (Blakeney) on the descent part. A clear slot was observed to the north during the descent. The profile showed a gradual decrease with height of the aerosol rather than a strong capping. The run was resumed at 500ft heading towards pt 40. Concentrations were much lower here than further north. A turn was made before pt 41 was reached (concs lower still) and we backtracked at 500ft heading north. A final profile ascent was made from 500ft to FL100 (finishing over land) passing pt 87. The top of the aerosol was about 6000ft.

EVUK71 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 19 Sep 2008 1010 UTC

S. R. Osborne (written 23-09-08).

Mission Scientist's Log

VACAR/ADIANT

S. R. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.402**.....

Date19/09/08.....

Page1... of6.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	Pre - take	DA	Wx	Cranfield	Baker cloud, some satellite
	Old frontal cloud			at various levels, mainly medium level?	
0848	(1006 Z)	satellite	overpass		Light haze whilst taking T/O CRANFIELD.
					Pretty hazy after T/O. Looks like 'white smoke', like mist!
					→ Bodes well for Waybourne later in the day.
	in climb	9300' ↗			2500/c on PASS.
		11,750'			thin cloud layer. Other cloud above in cloud → ACu.
		12,750'			* above cloud * clear of Ci above - good sign.
085405	TOP OF	(neph) AEROSOL	WAS	AS	2000 → ~ 6500 feet. Can see two aerosol layers + above the aged layers? Clear slot between them. Neph quite low during ascent but a few wiggles. 2/9 cloud.
090600	TRANSIT	FL210			Sheet below us breaking up ahead. (over land) continuous sheet to left, large breaks to right (over sea).
0914	climbing	FL258 ↗			large breaks in S ₁ to over right - NO GORE!
0932		FL270	346	55°18' N 10°18' W	Straight aheads looks better - probably over cloud edge. variable
093715	TRANS	FL270	346	55°41' 10°24'	
093922	RT	FL270	345	55°48' 10°24'	SONDE #1 Start Run going north.
094411	PI	FL270	344	56°18' N 10°36'	SONDE #2

Mission Scientist's Log

VACAR SECTION

Flight No **B.402**.....

Date 19/09/08.....

Page 2 of 6.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
094520	R1	FL270	344	56°24'N 1°36'W	cloud broken just to our right.
094738	R1	FL270	344	56°30' 1°38'	Seems dc below + ahead, manage SONDE #3 ARIES did not start zenith view - but had it for all ca into SE ahead - 500 (over land)
094959					
095123	R1	FL270	344	56°48' 1°42'	SONDE #4. → parked GPS.
095342	R1	FL270	346	57°01' 1°48'	SONDE #5 (extra one).
095332					
095504	R1	FL270	339	57°6' 1°48'	point B now. MARSS - during End Run (north of point B) + left below
100020	R2	FL270	109	57°0' 1°42'	Start Run.
100201	R2	FL270	195	56°48' 1°36'	SONDE #6 winds ^{mb} 22 @ 312°.
100350	R2	FL270			cloud breaks to our left and right but still st on our track.
100429	R2	FL270	174	56°56' 1°42'	SONDE #7
100722	R2	FL270	174	56°18' 1°36'	SONDE #8 <u>IASI overpass</u>
101011					Cloud breaking below us (con sec on lower VIS plot)
101051	R2	FL270	174	55°54' 1°24'	SONDE #9 to End Run.
101248	R2	FL270	174	55°42' 1°24'	End Run? + turn right.
102104	P12	FL270	001	55°54' 1°30'	Start profile descent → cloud free (last sonde splatted down (e.p.p.m.)) 1000 #/in
103123	P12	FL270	345	56°42' 1°42'	Restart profile (ATC).
103437	P12	FL270	169	56°36' 1°36'	Re-start profile.
10378	~FL140				Increase in aerosol (PCASP)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 402.....

Date 19/09/09.....

Page 3 of 6.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1041	PI ↓	FL110 ↓	171		
104251	PI →	FL090 →	171	56° 0' / 1° 24'	cloud thinned out below us Very broken (rearing point A) Interrupt.
104739	PI ↓	FL090 ↓	345	55° 54' / 1° 30'	Re-start; clear below! Cloud edge ahead.
105020					500 ft/min
105121				56° 17' / 1° 30'	over cloud edge! (just above)
105234					Hit cloud → fairly even tops, not "insp".
	PI ↓	4200'			cloud base. No cloud below the sea.
105659	PT →	3000'	350	56° 30' / 1° 36'	Low mass (tops) ≈ 0.2g/cm ³
105846	PI ↓	3000' ↓	348	56° 36' / 1° 42'	Interrupt (AIC) Re-start profile descent
					Good VTS in MBL → very little pollution here.
110446	PI	100'	352	57° 0' / 1° 48'	< Cloud clearing at point B > End profile at point B (roughly)
110531	S2.1 ↑	058		57° 0' / 1° 48'	(SS 2-3) Start sawtooths. Through cloud.
110530	S2.2	6000'	058	57° 0'	v- light cloud on this slope End first ascent / start next descent
111510		4600'			* Horizontal DOWN for a few mins *
111640	S2.2 / S2.3	4000'	173	56° 24' / 1° 36'	Hit cloud.
111927	S2.3 / S2.4	5000'			Reverse climb just below cloud base
		5500'		56° 17' / 1° 30'	TOPS
					Reverse

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.402**.....

Date **19/09/08**.....

Page **4** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		4900'			9L again about 0.22 g/m ³ max.
112242	S2-4	4000'	173	55°54'	TOPS. Suggest 4700-4800' reverse for in cloud run.
~1123					Cloud breaking
112408	S2-5	4750'	173	55°54' 1°24'	End sample in cloud (cloudy in run)
112551	R2	4750'	173	56°00' 1°24'	cloud temp ~ 4.8°C.
					Start run at mid-cloud level. (in clear at start, though)
112818		4750'			Skimming tops * CUI / AMS SLR
113355		~4800'			↳ good for cloud top Ref
113422	P3 ↓	~4760'	345	56°30' 1°36'	Out of cloud (END OF CUI bit)
113849	P3 ↓	~2000'			End run / Start profile descent. Below v. thin SL now
114306	P3	500'	347	57°00' 1°48'	prob. not good for in-situ anyway
114414	R3	500'	205	57°09' 1°48'	End profile descent (sharp turn) start run (hdg SMI changing). cloud, cloud broken + thin
114910	R3	500'			Bugge on aerosol here.
~1152					Next visib from ~ zero !!!
~1155		500'	171	58°18' 1°36'	some structure intact → dropping again. neph / Nox / AMS (sulphate) mainly sing.
115920					Can see haze ahead, darker to the left
120114			172	56°00' 1°30'	Edge of thin cloud ahead now, looks clear ahead.
120226	R3/R4	500'	179	55°54' 1°30'	VIS improving again, neph dropping off. End run (Start AMP/IP hot day)

Point A
Point B

Mission Scientist's Log

NOISE ON PEASP
Channel again

Flight No **B.402**.....

Date **19/09/08**.....

Page **5** of **6**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1213	R4	500'			Gsp (0.57) $\approx 10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ Fairly slow
1214					good VTS out of the window.
121635					broken cloud above us.
					Point 78 now. \rightarrow flying by
122230			142	54°48' N 10°0' W	'described' looks to R/H/S. PEASP into more pollution = <u>ice side?</u>
					<u>LOCALISED</u> \rightarrow Very hazy to left, clearer to right
122438	R4	500'	143	54°48' N 0°54' W	Good plume structure on right
122700					point 79 now
					looking hazier ahead now.
1232	R4	500'			\rightarrow west, sort of. Still visible
123630			142	54°48' N 0°12' W	Nept signal is still "plumey" Bigger plume yet, Gsp $\approx 50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
					PEASP - 1200/c.
124134	R4	500'	143	54°48' N 0°0' W	winds 3 m/s @ 260°. <u>SS = 2</u>
124300					point 80
					Now we hit the PEAC pollution.
					Gsp (0.55) $\approx 80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
124510					clear skies above.
124800					Gsp $\approx 110 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ <u>YES</u> good peaks.
					New record: $125 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
125341		500'	150	53°24' N 0°36' W	V-good separation in 3 ks.
					End Run / Start profile climb. to above aerosol layer if possible.
					No cap to aerosol \rightarrow peeks out slowly with height.

MAY

$\Gamma_{\text{obs}} = 24 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$

MAX:

$\Gamma_{\text{SP}} = 130 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.402**.....

Date 19/09/08.....

Page 6 of 6

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130014		FLO70	153	53°06' N 0°48' E	End ascent / Start descent
130231		FLO50			Can over land
130500		2200'			Blakeney (87) in descent clear slot to the mid-left? clear skies. Aerosol / scattering low here for equiv. height
130952		500'	108	52°48' N 1°3'	End profile descent / Start run
131139		500'	139	52°48' N 1°48' E	point 40 + turn. (51)
131830					$\Gamma_{\text{SP}} \approx 35 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ steady Better VLS here.
132300		500'	2	52°06' N 1°47' E	TURN → end of Routing
133603	P3.2	500'	31	52°48' N 1°48' E	moderate → wet neph $\text{CF}_3 = 1.7 - 1.8$?
133654	PS7	500'	285	52°48' N 1°41' E	point 40 + left turn End Run / Start profile ascent Inv's Blakeney Pt
134120		FLO55			Cones dropped at 1000-3000ft, then rising again. (2 layers in neb?) light can to our left → just over land now.
134230	PS7	FLO65		52°54' N 1°06' E	just coming out of descent clear of aerosol layers now. (before Blakeney)
134450	PS7	FLO88			(just before abeam Waybourne)
134545	PS	FL100	235	52°54' N 0°54' E	left turn (ATC) End profile climbs + end science

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B402

Date: 19/09/08 Operator: PDR DRS time: DAU1 time: DAU2 time: DAU3 time: AUX1 time: AUX2 time: Page 1 of 1
 Pcasp flow 0.84, vref 7.3, ffssp vref 3.5, 2dc end element voltages

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
07:34:20																2dp not run due to noise	
08:56:00																Switched off pcasp pump to see if/when noise starts	
09:16:00	30															No noise on pcasp seen	
09:19:00	50															Increase from 5-10	
09:21:00	25																
09:24:00	40															May be noise? Mostly in ch1	
09:29:00	50															Counts steadily increasing – almost certainly noise	
10:10:00	40															Increase from about 20. Possible feature or perhaps just increased noise	
10:21:00	40															Another increase from about 20 just before start of profile descent	
10:31:30	0															Noise from cold at high altitude gone	
10:34:00	10															Started to read aerosol again fl170	
10:53:00	1000					2000										In cloud, lwc and Pip anso working and saw cloud CIP saw no cloud fl47	
10:58:00	40															Low concentrations below cloud but increasing during descent	
11:02:00	40															Fl 10	
11:04:50	300															120 ft – bottom of profile.	
11:08:00	50															Fl 40	
11:12:00	80															Fl 60	
11:17:30	60	180				180										Fl 50	
11:20:00	30															Fl 50	
11:22:45	7															Fl 38	
11:24:10	25															Fl 45 5 spikes of noise seen in pcasp over last 5 mins	
11:28:00	12															Fl 45 one more spike of noise seen on pcasp	
11:32:00	300					500											
11:35:00	10															Fl 40 lots of noise spikes on pcasp	
11:56:00	600																
12:24:00	900															Rise from ~300 passing chemical works	
12:31:00	800																
12:36:00	1000																
12:42:00	1800																
12:48:00	3000																
12:54:00	1500																
13:00:15	100															Fl 65	
13:09:00	1300															500 ft	
13:25:30	800																
13:37:30	300															Fl 10	
13:45:00	60															Fl 90	
14:04:00																Switched off pcasp pump by mistake. Switched straight back on	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B402 **T/O:** 08:46:33
Date of flight: 19/09/08 **Land:** 14:06:59

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B402
Date of Flight: 19/09/08

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	15757 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 160511
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 42819 Blocks written = 42819 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 084000 End = 141500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images No 2dp Good 2dc images 1052 – 1133 mix liq/ice Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 2dc 10 pages

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b402_tas</p> <p>Start = 083000 End = 143000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 1113345 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 1490</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B402
Date of Flight: 19/09/08

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.84
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b402_tas_pcasp Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check. Noise on PCASP approx 1120 to 1205?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B402	Date	19/09/2008	Operator	KFT	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
094136	1	Launch	344.20 -35.90 49.04 312.70 26.80 0.70 -1.522700 56.067500 8232.00
095039	1	Splashdown	1023.45 12.71 86.32 232.19 4.36 -10.80 -1.422870 55.968822 -206.98
	1	TX to MetDB	End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.
094415	2	Launch	344.20 -35.80 43.14 313.80 27.40 0.60 -1.590200 56.272800 8232.60
095441	2	Splashdown	1023.78 12.93 87.47 266.04 6.85 -11.31 -1.498596 56.233045 -217.41
	2		End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.
094742	3	Launch	344.10 -36.00 43.07 310.80 27.80 0.50 -1.678300 56.540300 8233.30
095755	3	Splashdown	1023.46 12.88 86.42 255.43 6.51 -10.82 -1.589698 56.501083 -216.54
	3	TX to MetDB	End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.
095130	4	Launch	344.20 -35.50 33.30 310.70 26.60 0.80 -1.778500 56.835900 8232.60
100137	4	Splashdown	1023.58 12.68 84.62 243.66 6.04 -11.05 -1.686366 56.794900 -208.94
	4		End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Late GPS.
095348	5	Launch	344.20 -35.60 34.76 309.50 27.60 0.40 -1.830600 57.017000 8230.80
100359	5	Splashdown	1023.26 12.94 83.95 231.93 6.15 -6.39 -1.736649 56.979083 -204.18
	5		End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.
100203	6	Launch	343.80 -35.60 38.78 312.60 22.80 0.50 -1.697600 56.876500 8240.40
101214	6	Splashdown	1022.24 12.69 86.31 237.86 5.57 -11.07 -1.606119 56.840478 -200.71
	6	TX to MetDB	End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.
100433	7	Launch	343.90 -35.50 41.42 317.50 21.90 0.70 -1.711100 56.633700 8237.00
101444	7	Splashdown	1022.98 12.73 87.27 251.32 6.30 -11.40 -1.624947 56.598807 -209.20
	7		End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Late GPS
100733	8	Launch	344.20 -36.00 23.89 316.90 23.10 0.60 -1.609200 56.333900 8232.00
101739	8	Splashdown	1023.80 12.89 88.93 262.38 6.66 -11.06 -1.525763 56.311299 -219.61
	8	TX to MetDB	End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.
101057	9	Launch	344.20 -35.80 48.04 318.50 22.00 0.40 -1.499500 55.993600 8232.00
102110	9	Splashdown	1023.84 13.15 82.02 243.22 4.55 -10.37 -1.415979 55.957275 -223.53
	9		End-cap and parachute loosened prior to launch. Good drop.

B402CVI.txt

9/19/08 9:40:44 AM Point alpha first sonde and coincident start of run 1
9/19/08 9:53:45 AM At point B
9/19/08 9:55:14 AM end of run 1
9/19/08 10:00:19 AM 6th sonde and coincident start of run 2
9/19/08 10:02:02 AM Sorry - sonde 6 not released until now
9/19/08 10:07:44 AM satellite overpass now (didn't see it though)
9/19/08 10:10:55 AM end of run 2 at point A
9/19/08 10:21:06 AM start of stepped profile 1 descent at point a
9/19/08 10:31:38 AM interrupt of profile 1
9/19/08 10:34:39 AM re-start of profile 1 from point b
9/19/08 10:42:52 AM interrupt of profile 1 at point a
9/19/08 10:47:42 AM re-start profile 1 at point a
9/19/08 10:54:41 AM below cloud (sc5)
9/19/08 10:56:57 AM interrupt profile 1
9/19/08 10:58:53 AM re-start profile 1
9/19/08 11:05:18 AM end of profile 1
9/19/08 11:08:02 AM start of saw tooth 2.1 at b o heading to a
9/19/08 11:08:48 AM into cvi mode
9/19/08 11:11:29 AM very thin sc 5
9/19/08 11:12:11 AM start of profile 2.2
9/19/08 11:12:19 AM descent
9/19/08 11:15:20 AM into cloud
9/19/08 11:16:41 AM climbing on profile 2.3
9/19/08 11:19:20 AM above thin sc5
9/19/08 11:19:40 AM start of profile 2.4
9/19/08 11:21:05 AM into cloud
9/19/08 11:22:04 AM below 6/8 sc5
9/19/08 11:23:02 AM end of profile 2,4 start of 2.5
9/19/08 11:23:47 AM into cloud
9/19/08 11:24:20 AM end of profile 2.5
9/19/08 11:25:56 AM start of run 2
9/19/08 11:27:47 AM into sc5
9/19/08 11:34:23 AM end of run 2
9/19/08 11:34:37 AM start of rprofile descent 3
9/19/08 11:41:53 AM just passed ship
9/19/08 11:43:07 AM end of profile
9/19/08 11:44:26 AM start of run 3
9/19/08 11:46:21 AM another ship passed
9/19/08 12:41:44 PM point 80
9/19/08 12:53:42 PM start of profile climb

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 402

page 1 of 1

Date: 19/9/08 Operator(s): D. T. WIDEMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VACAR N SEA

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
	N3	1min CH					} N3
		3min N					
		1min CH					} Z3
		3min Z					
		30s CH					} NZ
		30s N					
		30s CH					
		30s Z					
094000	Run 1 FL270	Z3		0	70.04 70.66	30.34 30.52	Point A
094414					70.59	30.70	Script stopped after 1 cycle
094432	Run 1 FL270	N3		0	70.66	30.44	
095510	"	"		0	71.10	30.67	Script stopped Run end past point B
100630	Run 2 FL270	N3		C	70.71	30.19	Point B
101130	"	"		C	70.63	30.31	Script stopped end of run
101140	H	1x60	CBB	C	70.78	30.64	
101210	"	1x60	HBB	C	70.61	30.75	
11:43:55	N3 5008	NZ		0	70.50	30.42	Script stopped at Alpha.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	19/09/08	Flight	B402	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	VACAR/ADIENT			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

System start MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on			at time	06:33			
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	17°C	Ch	17°C	Ch18	17°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on			at time	06:34			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	287.2	Cold	284.7			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	06:37			
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		X

Deimos

Deimos Orientation (Nadir or Zenith)							Z
Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software			at time	06:39			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	286.4	Cold	285.6			
Target heating							X
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual		X
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	08:38			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.57	Cold	288.15		
	Deimos:	Hot	344.91	Cold	301.97		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	55.7	14.1	56.7	16.5			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	39.6	32.98	37.14	41.98	43.151		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Flight #	B402	Date	19/09/08	Operator(s)	Pollard	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

Data Processing Log		Initials	Date
Flight data copied from MARSS/Deimos PC flash disk to Martian C:\Bxxx\		DP	19/09/08
Check disc space on flash disk (need >~10 MB free)		DP	19/09/08
Copy* Martian logged data from to C:\Bxxx\		DP	19/09/09
Wave processing run and BT files generated		DP	14/11/08
DQM file generated and uploaded		DP	14/11/08
NetCDF file generated and uploaded		DP	14/11/08
Data processing issues/notes:			

B402_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

07:31:40.64 --- - - - -
07:31:40.64 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:31:40.64 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:31:40.64 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B402
07:31:40.64 --- - - - -
07:32:10.37 SWS - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
07:32:11.96 SWS - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
07:32:15.60 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
07:32:15.60 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
07:32:22.38 USH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
07:32:23.61 USH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
07:32:23.71 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:32:25.75 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
07:32:25.75 USH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
07:32:30.11 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:32:32.26 LSH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
07:32:33.92 LSH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
07:32:36.88 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
07:32:36.89 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
07:32:38.69 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:32:43.09 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:32:48.46 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
07:32:50.12 SWS 173.4 - - - Telescope stopped.
07:32:57.59 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
07:32:58.70 SWS 90.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
07:33:01.45 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:33:15.74 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:33:15.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:33:15.76 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:33:17.72 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:33:18.06 SWS - - - - Idling
07:33:20.18 USH - - - - Idling
07:33:21.57 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:33:21.57 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:33:23.00 SWS - - - - Idling
07:33:25.21 USH - - - - Idling
07:33:26.94 LSH - - - - Idling
07:33:27.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:33:27.53 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
07:33:27.54 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:39:27.83 --- - - - -
08:39:27.83 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:39:27.83 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:39:27.83 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B402
08:39:27.83 --- - - - -
08:39:50.53 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:40:01.93 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
08:40:07.65 SWS - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
08:40:09.10 SWS - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
08:40:14.32 USH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
08:40:15.73 USH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
08:40:19.28 LSH - 1000 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 1000ms.
08:40:21.36 LSH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
08:40:23.65 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
08:40:23.65 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
08:40:27.50 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
08:40:27.50 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
08:40:31.10 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
08:40:31.10 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
08:48:55.17 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:50:46.59 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:50:52.21 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:50:54.55 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:51:07.18 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:51:07.18 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

08:51:07.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:07.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:51:08.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:51:09.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:51:09.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:51:09.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:51:18.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:51:19.00	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:51:22.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:51:27.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:27.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:27.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:28.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:51:29.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:51:29.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:51:37.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:51:42.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:51:42.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:51:42.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:54:01.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:01.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:02.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:05.35	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
08:54:05.36	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
08:54:07.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:54:07.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:54:07.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:54:08.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:54:09.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:10.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:11.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:54:11.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:54:13.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:13.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:18.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:54:18.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:54:18.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:54:18.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:55:01.35	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
08:55:04.58	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -8.000
08:57:20.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:20.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:20.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:22.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:22.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:22.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:24.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:57:24.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:25.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:25.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:25.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:27.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:28.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:31.87	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
08:57:31.87	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
08:57:33.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:33.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:33.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:33.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:36.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:36.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:38.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:39.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:39.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:40.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:57:42.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:44.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:44.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:57:44.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

08:57:45.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:57:45.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:57:45.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:58:44.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 14 deg C
08:59:15.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:16.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:59:24.70	SWS	-8.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 172.000
08:59:26.37	SWS	168.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:59:32.21	SWS	172.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 172.000
08:59:35.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:38.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:59:38.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:39.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:59:43.34	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 75ms.
08:59:43.35	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 75ms.
08:59:44.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:59:46.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:59:47.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:50.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:59:54.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:59:57.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:00:00.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:00:01.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:00:04.82	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
09:00:06.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:21.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:22.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:22.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:24.13	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:09:28.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:28.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:28.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:29.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:09:29.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:30.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:30.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:30.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:31.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:32.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:33.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:33.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:33.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:33.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:34.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:35.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:09:36.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:36.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:38.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:39.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:39.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:39.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:12.71	SWS	172.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.000
09:10:14.12	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.000
09:11:27.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
09:18:15.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:15.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:15.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:17.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:17.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:17.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:18.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:18.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:18:20.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:20.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:20.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:21.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:22.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:23.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:23.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

09:18:25.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:26.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:26.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:27.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:27.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:27.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:29.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:32.85	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
09:18:32.85	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
09:18:33.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:35.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:36.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:18:37.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:38.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:38.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:38.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:26.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:27.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:27.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:28.59	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:32:32.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:32.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:32.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:33.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:32:34.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:34.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:35.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:35.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:36.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:37.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:38.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:38.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:39.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:40.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:41.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:41.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:32:42.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:42.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:43.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:46.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:46.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:46.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:36:15.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:15.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:15.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:19.35	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:36:20.80	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:36:24.85	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:36:33.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:33.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:33.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:34.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:36:34.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:36.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:36.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:36.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:38.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:39.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:40.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:40.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:42.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:42.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:43.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:43.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:43.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:43.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:36:45.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:46.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:36:54.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

09:37:44.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:44.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:44.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:45.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:37:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:37:46.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:37:47.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:47.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:48.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:37:49.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:37:54.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:37:54.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:54.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:54.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:39:34.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:34.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:34.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:39.21	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:39:44.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:44.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:44.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:45.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:39:45.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:47.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:47.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:47.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:49.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:49.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:50.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:50.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:39:50.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:52.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:39:55.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:34.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:34.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:34.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:35.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:40:35.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:37.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:37.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:37.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:40:39.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:39.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:44.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:45.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:45.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:45.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:41:10.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
09:51:42.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
09:55:06.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:06.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:06.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:08.59	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:55:15.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:15.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:15.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:17.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:55:17.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:18.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:18.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:18.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:20.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:21.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:22.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:22.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:23.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:24.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:24.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:25.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

09:55:25.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:25.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:55:26.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:27.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:28.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:43.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:43.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:43.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:56:44.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:56:45.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:46.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:56:54.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:12.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:13.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:13.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:14.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:59:15.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:16.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:23.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:53.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:53.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:53.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:55.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:59:55.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:56.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:04.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:07.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:07.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:07.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:08.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:00:08.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:09.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:17.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:21.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:21.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:21.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:37.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
10:12:46.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:47.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:47.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:49.01	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:12:53.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:53.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:53.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:55.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:12:55.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:56.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:56.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:56.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:58.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:59.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:00.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:00.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:02.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:03.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:04.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:05.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:05.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:05.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:06.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:13:07.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:07.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:16.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:07.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:07.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:07.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:09.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:17:09.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:10.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:17:11.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:11.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:12.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:14.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:15.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:15.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:17.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:18.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:18.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:46.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
10:17:48.48	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
10:19:21.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:21.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:21.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:23.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:19:24.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:24.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:24.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:24.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:26.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:27.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:29.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:29.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:31.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:32.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:32.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:34.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:34.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:34.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:36.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:19:36.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:37.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:38.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:38.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:39.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:40.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:41.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:41.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:19:42.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:43.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:19:45.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:20.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:20.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:20.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:21.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:20:22.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:22.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:22.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:24.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:24.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:24.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:25.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:27.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:27.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:27.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:29.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:29.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:20:31.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:21:06.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:06.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:21:06.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:24.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:24.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:25.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:27.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:27.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:27.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:29.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:31:29.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:31:30.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:31.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:31.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:32.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:34.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:38.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:38.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:38.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:38.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:40.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:41.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:41.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:41.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:43.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:44.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:49.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:49.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:49.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:49.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:50.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:51.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:52.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:52.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:54.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:55.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:55.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:55.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:57.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:58.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:00.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:32:11.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
10:33:36.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:36.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:36.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:37.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:33:38.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:39.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:39.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:39.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:41.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:42.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:42.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:42.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:33:44.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:45.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:33:46.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:11.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:11.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:11.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:14.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:14.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:14.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:24.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:24.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:24.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:53.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:54.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:54.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:57.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:43:08.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:08.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:08.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:09.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:43:09.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:11.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:12.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:12.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:14.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:15.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:43:16.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:16.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:17.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:18.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:19.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:20.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:20.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:20.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:21.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:43:21.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:23.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:24.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:24.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:26.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:27.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:29.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:29.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:30.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:31.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:32.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:32.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:32.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:32.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:34.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:43:34.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:35.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:36.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:36.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:38.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:38.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:39.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:39.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:41.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:42.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:43:43.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:51.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:51.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:51.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:53.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:45:53.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:54.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:02.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:03.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:03.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:03.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:05.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:46:05.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:06.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:14.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:41.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:41.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:41.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:43.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:46:43.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:44.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:45.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:45.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:46.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:47.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:48.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:48.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:50.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:50.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:52.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:47:09.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
10:47:43.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:43.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:47:43.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:28.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

10:53:31.33	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 100ms.
10:53:34.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:53:38.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:53.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:55:54.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:03.91	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
10:56:05.61	SWS	-3.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:56:06.54	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
10:56:10.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:11.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:12.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:02.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:02.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:02.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:05.34	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:57:09.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:09.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:09.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:10.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:57:11.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:12.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:13.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:14.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:15.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:20.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:22.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:22.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:22.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:57:24.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:57:24.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:25.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:29.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:29.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:33.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:57:36.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:14.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:58:17.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:18.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:20.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:25.18	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:58:25.19	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
10:58:25.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:58:26.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:28.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:30.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:31.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:33.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:36.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:58:37.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:40.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:41.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:43.98	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:58:43.99	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:58:45.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:58:47.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:48.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:49.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:58:50.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:50.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:58:50.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:06.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
11:04:49.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:49.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:04:49.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:07.16	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:05:11.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:11.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:11.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:05:12.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:13.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:05:13.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:14.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:14.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:15.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:15.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:17.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:17.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:18.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:18.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:19.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:19.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:20.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:21.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:05:22.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:19.25	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:07:20.97	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:07:22.58	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:07:31.36	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.000
11:07:32.82	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.000
11:07:34.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:34.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:34.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:36.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:07:36.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:36.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:45.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:51.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:51.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:51.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:54.19	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
11:11:55.64	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
11:17:00.32	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.000
11:17:02.91	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 173.000
11:19:29.30	SWS	173.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
11:19:31.32	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 176.000
11:20:05.59	SWS	176.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 175.000
11:20:07.05	SWS	175.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 175.000
11:22:46.25	SWS	175.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 172.000
11:22:48.85	SWS	172.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 172.000
11:24:12.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:12.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:12.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:14.52	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:24:18.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:18.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:18.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:19.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:20.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:24:20.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:20.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:20.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:22.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:22.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:24.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:24.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:25.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:25.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:28.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:28.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:29.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:29.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:29.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:30.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:30.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:30.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:31.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:31.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:24:31.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:24:41.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:41.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:41.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:41.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:24:43.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:43.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:24:43.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:24:52.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:09.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
11:25:25.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:25.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:25.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:26.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:27.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:25:27.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:36.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:52.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:52.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:52.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:55.86	SWS	172.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:27:56.79	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:34:24.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:24.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:25.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:26.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:26.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:26.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:28.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:28.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:34:28.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:37.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:37.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:37.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:37.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:38.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:38.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:48.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:48.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:48.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:48.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:34:49.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:50.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:34:59.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:02.40	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:35:04.11	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:35:05.59	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:35:08.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:08.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:08.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:09.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:35:09.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:09.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:18.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:35:36.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 8 deg C
11:36:23.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:23.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:23.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:24.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:36:24.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:24.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:36:33.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:33.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:33.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:37:53.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:08.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:08.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:09.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:13.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

11:43:14.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:18.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:43:20.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:25.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:26.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:28.84	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:43:33.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:33.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:33.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:35.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:35.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:43:35.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:42.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:42.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:44.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:44.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:44.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:50.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:50.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:50.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:52.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:43:52.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:43:52.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:01.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:06.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:06.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:06.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:44:07.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:44:07.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:07.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:16.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:16.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:44:16.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:44:18.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:28.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:28.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:28.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:30.47	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:02:33.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:33.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:33.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:34.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:34.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:35.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:02:35.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:36.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:36.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:37.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:38.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:38.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:38.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:39.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:40.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:42.96	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
12:02:42.97	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
12:02:44.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:45.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:45.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:45.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:46.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:02:46.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:46.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:49.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:49.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:50.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:50.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:52.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:52.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:02:54.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

12:02:54.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:02:55.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:03:03.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:03.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:03.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:04:44.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
12:06:05.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:06:08.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:06:16.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:08:19.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:08:20.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:21.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:21.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:23.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:23.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:08:23.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:23.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:29.69	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
12:08:29.69	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
12:08:33.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:34.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:37.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:37.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:41.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:44.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:44.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:29.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:09:58.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:10:02.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:10:03.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:04.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:06.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:08.00	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:10:08.01	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:10:09.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:10:10.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:10:11.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:47.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:10:59.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:11:05.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:11:14.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:11:15.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:18.15	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
12:11:18.17	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
12:11:19.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:20.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:21.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:27.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:11:44.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:11:45.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:46.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:48.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:49.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:55.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:11:57.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:11:58.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:59.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:12:08.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:12:09.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:12.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:12.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:13.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:15.04	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:27:18.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:18.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:18.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:19.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:20.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

12:27:21.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:21.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:21.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:22.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:23.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:24.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:24.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:25.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:25.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:26.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:26.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:27.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:27.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:28.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:28.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:29.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:29.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:29.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:31.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:31.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:31.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:08.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
12:42:32.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:32.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:32.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:37.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:37.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:37.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:38.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:42:38.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:39.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:39.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:39.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:41.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:41.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:42.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:42.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:43.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:44.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:45.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:45.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:42:46.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:47.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:47.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:42:48.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:48.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:42:48.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:53:42.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:42.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:42.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:44.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:44.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:44.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:53:45.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:45.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:53:46.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:55.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:53:57.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:54:01.45	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
12:54:02.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:02.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:02.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:40.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:00:41.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:00:43.28	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
13:00:45.33	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
13:00:47.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:00.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:00.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:09:00.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:04.45	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:09:08.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:08.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:08.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:09.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:09.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:09:10.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:12.27	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:09:13.75	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:09:14.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:14.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:15.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:16.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:16.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:16.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:09:18.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:18.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:19.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:09:20.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:20.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:20.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:09:58.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 10 deg C
13:23:07.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:07.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:07.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:13.82	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:23:17.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:17.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:18.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:18.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:23:19.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:22.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:22.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:23.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:24.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:24.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:24.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:25.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:26.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:27.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:28.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:28.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:28.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:30.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:30.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:32.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:32.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:32.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:34.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:34.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:34.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:35.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:36.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:37.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:37.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:23:38.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:39.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:23:39.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:11.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:11.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:11.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:12.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:13.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:24:14.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:15.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:15.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:24:16.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:17.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:18.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:18.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:19.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:20.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:22.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:35.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:35.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:35.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:25:01.19	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
13:25:02.70	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.000
13:26:15.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 8 deg C
13:35:49.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:49.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:49.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:50.32	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:35:53.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:53.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:53.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:54.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:55.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:35:56.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:59.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:35:59.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:00.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:01.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:01.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:01.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:02.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:03.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:04.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:07.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:07.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:07.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:08.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:08.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:36:09.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:10.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:10.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:11.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:12.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:14.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:14.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:15.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:16.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:17.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:17.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:18.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:18.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:20.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:28.02	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
13:36:30.10	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -9.000
13:36:36.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:36.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:36.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:47.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:47.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:47.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:48.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:48.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:48.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:49.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:49.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:45:50.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:51.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:51.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:52.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:53.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:45:54.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:54.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:55.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:56.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:57.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:57.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:58.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:59.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:59.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:12.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 9 deg C
13:46:14.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** endex
13:46:24.41	SWS	-9.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
13:46:25.59	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

Flight:

B402

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B402

Date: 19/09/08

Instruments

1. Neph comms – Problems communicating with dry neph pre-flight on com 2. Works on com 1 (normally used by wet neph). Tried swapping dry neph to com 3 (normally psap), that works. Left it there. Suspect intermittent connections on USB / Serial hub.
2. CPC – could not get AIM software to run, i.e. would not go past Error messages “The parameter is not correct” and AIM MFC Application Error. Pre-flight and inflight
3. About Time – MARSS pc updating to BST rather than UTC after t/o.
4. Headset – AVAPS too quiet / muffled on transmission for Cptn to hear. Swap Lightspeed Zulu with CCM1 Telex, then much clearer.
5. Mission Scientist laptop – lost contact with Horace inflight. Suspect intermittent Ethernet connector.
6. PCASP – noisy bin 1
7. MPDS laptop – no connection for ~1/2 hour during initial transit, then okay.
8. RFC – Water droplets forming and running down camera window at 1235Z, (in clear air, 500’).
- 9.

CVI -
Neph –PSAP -
SWS -
SHIMS -
AMS / SP2 -
Core Chem -
Cloud physics -
FWVS,
TAFTS,
AVAPS,
ARIES,
MARSS,
DEIMOS

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Satpics, 0920, 0934 – VACAR

MPDS

Satpic - VACAR

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 19/9/8

Flight No: B 402

Pre-Flighter: Gna Hox

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	NR
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	NR
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	Not properly shut down previously?
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	} left to operate
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs	Checked & Cleaned	
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX	applied	
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
47	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

CCN - laptop '0117' software

EIEA11 MSG 3.9 micron Infrared Image 19 Sep 2008 0900 UTC

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 19 Sep 2008 1000 UTC

